

Selected, refused or opted out?

Emigration selection policies and migrant agency 1950s-1970s

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Introduction

The last 20 years saw a growing body of scholarship analysing the reasons for international variations in non-humanitarian immigration policy and -related to that- the role of selection criteria in the immigrant settlement process (Wright 2015; Cob-Clark 2000/2007). European states are compared with the more traditional non-European countries of destination like the US, Canada and Australia. Although most of the authors historicize this selective immigration policy, distinguishing in periods in which race, labour skills and family relations were factors that successively dominated and/or were relaxed, none of them take into account the perspective and policy of the countries of origin and they sometimes struggle with the analysis of individual actor behaviour. Here we focus on selection policy as a joint policy by emigration and immigration countries, taking the Dutch-Australian migration as a case study.

Some backgrounds

There was a large bottom-up wish to leave in the late 1940's, but Dutch emigration between 1945-1992 became strongly state-regulated. Actual policy making and implementation was delegated to a complex governance system of governmental and civil society bodies, that played an important part in pre-selection procedures. Dutch migration researchers have long been aware of this emigrant selection procedure and its complications after 1945 (Van Faassen 2001, Schrover and Van Faassen 2010). At a policy level the interests of the country of origin and that of destination there was a tension between the interests in terms of categories of people and employability. The administrative complications of post-World War II migrant selection led to the involvement of both government and non-government parties at both the policy and the executive level. Actual emigrant selection was carried out by the officials of local offices. In the Netherlands where there were still religious sectors or pillars, these were either the private emigration centres (with a religious signature) or the public regional employment centres. The ultimate decision was in the hands of the Australian immigration officers, based in the Netherlands. These selection procedures and their results - who applied for migration, who were selected and who actually left - have been understudied, mainly because of a focus on the emigration that really took place and the people involved in it. In this paper we concentrate on those who never left, although in some cases the 'never left' turned out to be relative.

From our project Migrant, in which we employ digital methods to create a new resource for the study of Dutch-Australian migration based on (pre)registration systems in the Netherlands and Australia, we know that large scale categorizations for migrants were made and applied during the entire selection stages by both states. This slide shows the data- axis

that we use to create a life course for the emigrant by linking the pre-selection card or file to the finalisation by the Netherlands Emigration Service (the so-called mastercard) to the application files, kept in the National Archives Australia. Today we concentrate on the pre-selection files (as shown in fig. 1, left above).

Fig. 1 Data axis with registration cards NED (source NA) and pre-selection cards CEC (source VU_HDC)

Selection Files

Our study concerns two sets of selection cards/files. The first is from the 'Emigratiebureau van de Bossche Diocesane bond der K.A.B.' (KAB) that is, the emigration office of the Catholic Worker Union in Tilburg, the second from the Christelijke Emigratie Centrale (CEC) with its national office in The Hague. In both archives the surviving application files for migration to Australia have been selected and both contain granted migrations as well as rejections and withdrawals. Neither archive is complete but the two archives constitute a considerable sample from the population of migrants, from two different periods of Dutch-Australian migration.

The KAB documentation mainly concerns the period 1954-1956 and we have studied all 618 applicants, 133 (21%) of whom emigrated, 175 (28 %) did not emigrate and 306 (48 %) files have and indeterminate outcome most of which will probably - we can speculate - having ended up in a non-departure. Of those who left 18 (13 %) were women and 115 (86 %) men, but as this concerns emigration units, the men also include the families.

The CEC applications contain circa 1850 cards (the actual files have been destroyed), of which we studied a sample of 182 applicants corresponding to 10 % of the total number of

cards. The CEC cards are predominantly from the late 1960 and early 1970s, when total migration numbers to Australia had diminished considerably compared to the 1950s (and the Dutch active emigration policy was relaxed). CEC procedures are a bit more evenly spread than those from the KAB with the peak years representing each between 10 and 19 percent of the cases. In the CEC case 53 percent of the applicants eventually departed, 32 percent withdrew and 16 percent were refused by Australia.

KAB cases were overwhelmingly from the east of the Brabant province in the southern Netherlands, which was to be expected as this was the area in which the union was active. All of the KAB migrants were catholics. The CEC migrants were from 93 different towns all over the country with a little concentration on the Randstad town from the western Netherlands. While the CEC was a protestant organisation, only 63 percent of the migrants were of a protestant denomination, 17 percent were Catholics and 17 percent had no religion and there were also 5 Muslims and 1 Hindu.

Fig.2 Distribution of pre-selection cards/files CEC-KDC over the years

We started from the scarce Dutch historiography that assumes that there is double selection (Schrover & Van Faassen) or that occupations were downcast (Fels) and we ourselves wonder whether the selection files are representative because we don't find higher educated people. And we try to model things, but then it turns out that if it says migrants were rejected, sometimes they left anyway. And sometimes they didn't. But then all that is not on the card in question, but on another card.

Procedures and interactions

When we studied the files in more detail, we realised that the procedure may seem strict and normative, but that in fact it had many more aspects. Therefore it should be

problematised more and the original title we proposed was too much geared towards the outcome of the procedure. But we now think it should be replaced by a new one that expresses better the interactions with the procedure. We renamed the our paper to: *Judgements and expectations. Assumptions that shaped the Dutch-Australian emigrant policy. An explorative analysis.*

The files are full of judgments (by the migration officers) and expectations (by the prospective migrants) (fig 3). Or so it seems - but it remains to be seen whose expectations and judgements are really in the files. We have selected some examples that made us doubt how fixed and normative the procedure really was.

Fig 3 Judgements and expectations

The first example actually would point at a strict coordination of the procedure. The questions to the migrants were highly harmonised between the different organisations that selected them. Three different instances from three different organisations and even periods are all more or less the same and contain the same questions. Notwithstanding the many different selection organisations, the contents of the files were coordinated.

were refused by the Dutch authorities. But Australia also had its wishes about what kind of labour-related skills they wanted their immigrants to bring and at least in the beginning they made yearly lists of these desiderata.

COMMONWEALTH OF AUSTRALIA

Schedule of the trade and work categories and the number of migrants to be selected in each category under the Australia/Netherlands Assisted Migration Agreement for the period 1st April, 1951 to 31st December, 1951, and their priority of shipment.

Nomination Number	Trade or Work Classification	Number of Persons to be Selected	Age Group	Male or Female	Marital Status	Priority of Shipment	Remarks
D.G.1	Carpenters	1,500	As set out in Instruction 3 of Procedural Instructions	Male	Single		If sufficient single men are not available to complete nomination, married couples may be drawn upon and lastly, family units may be accepted.
D.G.2	Bricklayers	300		Male	Single		Include 50 Roof Tilers
D.G.3	Plumbers	100		Male	Single		If sufficient single men are not available to complete nomination, married couples may be drawn upon and lastly, family units may be accepted.
D.G.4	Plasterers	100		Male	Single		
D.G.5	Painters	100		Male	Single		
D.G.6	Building Labourers	1,000		Male	Single		

Australian expectations

Assumption: we get the immigrants we need

Australian Desiderata about Dutch immigrants In 1951

Source: NL-HaNA 2.15.68 1164

Fig 6 Example of Australian desiderata

There were tensions between who Australia wanted and who the Dutch considered 'missable', but in the procedure the Dutch officers tried to fit the migrants to the Australian labour classification system.

This was the case in the 1950s and the 1960, only the coding system changed in the meantime. As far as we can establish, Australian requirements to Dutch migrants shifted over time. In the early 1950s they wanted only industrial labourers, and preferably single men. At the time, from the Catholic Union they did get mostly working class men. But besides single men there was a considerable amount of single women and married couples. In the 1960 there were many more migrants with administrative experience and still roughly the same mix of married couples and single men and women. At the time, decreasing Dutch emigrant numbers had led to adjustments in the migration schemes, most notably with the addition of a youth program to stimulate Dutch emigration again.

As economist Jan Fels already stated for the CEC- pre-selection cards, labour qualifications are fitted to the Australian Scheme, also for the KAB-cards in the 1950s. Fels doesn't explain the fact that skills mostly were lower ranked, but as correspondence between the local authorities in the Netherlands and Australia seem to suggest, this was a way to create a win-win situation to get migrants more easily accepted and besides we also found out that there

were problems with translating specific Dutch professions into Australian professions or skills.

Another assumption from the Dutch perspective is the importance of diploma's and the labour history of the emigrant. However, if we compare the preselection files with the application files in the National Archives Australia (of those who left), we find only a few of these testimonials translated and added to the file. Migrants complained about that. In addition, we know that diplomas are not often acknowledged (by the unions) and that most of the migrants seldom ended up in their original profession or combined jobs and often switched jobs.

As for the judgments of the Dutch selecting officers: with a few exceptions, judgments are remarkably alike and they were also (sort of) translated into English. The Catholic selection files where they are included are in this respect no real selection instrument and repeat that the prospective migrants are decent, honest and hardworking people who will certainly succeed in their migration. Either the officers left the selection to the Australians, or they tried to smoothen the procedure for as many migrants as possible.

The migrants themselves also tried to influence the procedure. We have already seen that they delivered their work testimonials and filled out all the forms. They also presented themselves as best they could. If we were to believe the application forms, they were nearly all learning English. But in a report from one of the migrant ships the official complained that none of the migrants could fill out the twenty-three English questions on an entrance form and it took him a lot of time to arrange matters satisfactorily.

Migrant assumptions

Assumptions: Learning English

15. Welke talen spreekt U behalve Nederlands? Zijn Engels als lerende

64 % claims to be learning English, but in practice migrants 'have too little command of English' to fill in the 23 questions on the 'incoming-passenger-cards'

Algemeene werkzaamheden:
Voor aankomst te Fremantle waren alle werkzaamheden gereed, die voor Austr-
lie gevraagd
het kantoor
aankomst te
blanco-model
moeten worde
gelsch kan s
het een groe
vertrek uit
te laten sta
kwamen. Zulks
voor elk lid
de kaarten d
slag nam. Zek
Zou het niet
boeking, of o
legatie klaa
ven. Ik vers
Gelijk met b
meester had
waren.

Since practically none of the immigrants can speak enough English to fill in this card, which contains 23 questions, it was a great advantage for them to have a clearly typed example. Before leaving the Netherlands, I had already asked Mr Giel to have a Dutch questionnaire stencilled, with all the questions on this inc. pass. card in his own language. This was done and on embarkation, every passenger received such a list for every member of the family. From these questionnaires, we made up the cards, a job that took an incredibly long time. Would it not be possible, in the future, for these cards to be prepared at passage booking, or at one of the offices such as the Foundation for Relocation or the Australian Legation? This would save us a lot of work. I kindly request your cooperation in this matter.

Source: Stadsarchief Rotterdam
Archief Lloyd 454-05, 586, p3

Fig 7 English proficiency

Other migrants also tried to squeeze in their wishes on the form. The most obvious way was by making their current job a little more important. Some also expressed their wish to emigrate with some other migrants, even if they were not certain that they would take the big step.

It is also significant that most of the migrants of the Union applied just after a program for subsidising emigration had been announced and many emphatically applied for this subsidy.

The procedure may seem fixed and intransigent and all parties involved did their utmost to provide all required information. But in the 1950s as well as the 1960s we also see migrants drop out of the procedure at all times. Even the form already warned that not appearing on the interview date would delay the procedure. But nearly half of the migrants never left, mostly with the simple remark that emigration was cancelled. Both the forms and the cards are full of migrants that get lost somewhere in the process, sometimes with giving notice of cancellation but often also by not showing up. This looks like migrant agency, but as we have seen throughout our project there are lots of factors and actors influencing both migrant policy and migrant agency and therefore the boundary between both is much more fluid, asking for explanations by analysing the migrant networks and the feedback loops to policy makers, often communicated via diplomatic channels.

Conclusion

We started this paper with the premise that the selection procedure was very strict and selective - given the many forms the migrants had to fill in. However, during the process of modelling and analysing the data it turned out that this was a too superficial as well as reductionist approach. There was no way to find out if 'refused' or 'opted out' outcome of the selection procedure was really the final word on whether aspiring migrants really stayed in the Netherlands. It is even harder to link this to a decision rooted in 'policy' or 'agency'. Therefore we decided to take one step back, zoom out a bit and problematize the selection procedure by giving more space to reconsider the forms themselves and the arguments found in them and relate them to the correspondence within and around the selection process. Selection forms are no longer just seen as bureaucratic pieces of a normative paper trail that can be modelled to a quantitative overview, but they also become information providers with regard to apparent-non migrants. This also leads to the conclusion that in order to be able to acknowledge the interaction between policy and migrants' choices it is necessary to have a better knowledge of surrounding actors and networks, in order to be able to differentiate between all sorts of factors influencing policy or individual decision making.

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